

Pre-session Questionnaire

Demographic questions

(examples of demographic questions that can be used in this session)

What is your age?

- 18–24 25–34 35–44 45–54 55+

What is your gender?

- Male Female Prefer not to say

Other: _____

What is your highest level of education?

- Primary Education Secondary Education Higher Education

Other: _____

How familiar are you with tools like...? *(describe a similar tool to your probe)*

- Not familiar Somewhat familiar Familiar Very familiar
-

Expectations

After hearing the explanation about the study context, tell us what your expectations are regarding the technology and its usage:

For the research team to fill - ID: _____